

CHLORINATION OF METAL SULPHIDES. PART VII. LEAD SULPHIDE

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With suitable rate of flow of chlorine gas, chlorine acts on lead sulphide affording elementary sulphur. The reaction is favoured with increase of temperature. Best results are, however, obtained (in the absence of any incorporate) at 400°-450°. At 500°, chlorination is very unsatisfactory due to fusion of the lead chloride formed.

Use of incorporates allows the chlorination to be carried out satisfactorily at 500°. Silica was quite satisfactory, but carbon was better than silica. Best results were obtained with sodium chloride as an incorporate. With this, it was possible under conditions of experiments to carry the reaction up to about 88.0% till the transition point (for formation of sulphur chlorides) was reached. About 80% of pure elementary sulphur was formed under these conditions.

Rose² observed that chlorine did not decompose galena at room temperature but quickly reacted at higher temperatures affording lead chloride and chlorides of sulphur. The reaction was found by Schafer³ to be rapid near the melting point of lead chloride (500°), with quantitative yield. Smith⁴ reported that galena was also decomposed by sulphur monochloride vapour at 250°. Lead sulphide is also known⁵ to undergo double decomposition with a number of metallic chlorides.

From our experience with the systems investigated earlier¹, it was felt that the formation of sulphur chloride, as reported by Rose² by the action of chlorine on lead sulphide, could possibly be checked by proper control of experimental conditions such as temperature, space velocity or use of incorporates, so as to obtain elementary sulphur out of this reaction. Experiments were thus carried out with this point in view and to find out the best conditions for the reaction :

EXPERIMENTAL

For the experimental set up and procedure for chlorination, the same practice was followed as described in one of the earlier papers⁶. The lead sulphide used for the various experiments was prepared in the laboratory according to the following procedure.

Lead acetate was dehydrated and then treated⁶ in the dry state with hydrogen sulphide at about 150°. The reaction was slow at this temperature and took a considerable time, but it was found more suitable than direct

sulphiding at 450°. After the major portion of the lead acetate had been converted into the sulphide, the temperature was raised to 400°-450° and the mass kept there for 10 to 15 hours while a very slow stream of hydrogen sulphide was passed. This helped the completion of sulphiding and also removal of the last traces of acetic acid formed. A very pure powdered sample was obtained (this contained 86.34% Pb; calc. for PbS: Pb, 86.2%. The sulphur content was 13.5%).

Analysis of the soluble product and insoluble residues was made according to standard procedure. Lead was determined by precipitating as lead chromate with known excess of standard dichromate and determining the excess of dichromate.

D I S C U S S I O N

By conducting a few preliminary experiments, a suitable rate of flow of chlorine was decided upon for final experiments. The first set of these experiments was carried out at different temperatures. Results are set out in Table I.

TABLE I

Chlorination of PbS at different temperatures.

PbS taken = 10 g. Duration of expt. = 3 hours. Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Temp.	Progress of reaction.	Residual sulphide.	Elem. S obtd.	Trans. point.	Nature of product.
200°	62.7%	36.9%	32.5%	2 hr. 0 min	Infused mass that could be easily powdered.
300°	69.6	30.0	36.3	2, 15	
400°	83.4	16.1	54.9	2 45	
450°	86.2	13.4	53.2	2 40	Semifused.
500°	17.5	82.1	9.5	2 5	Fused, very hard mass.

The general nature of the reaction was more or less the same as previously observed with other sulphides. Increasing of temperature has a tendency to favour the reaction :

But, beyond 450°, the product was obtained as a very hard mass and it apparently hindered the action of chlorine. This explains the very unfavourable results at 500°. Even at 450°, the reaction is not much better than that at 400°. It seems improbable that the lead sulphide itself would fuse at such low temperatures, as it has a high melting point of 1114°. Lead chloride melts at about 500°, and it seems more probable that the lead chloride fuses and entraps the lead sulphide in it.

A series of reactions was next carried out at 400° with lead sulphide alone, without any incorporate. As the results in Table II would show, the reaction proceeded quite satisfactorily.

TABLE II

Progress of chlorination of PbS alone at 400°.

PbS taken = 10 g. Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Duration of expt.	Progress of reaction.	Residual sulphide.	Elem. S found.	Transition point.
1 hr.	25.0%	74.6%	16.4%	Not reached
2	55.0	44.5	46.3	Do
2 hr. 50 min.	78.9	20.6	69.5	Just reached
3	83.4	16.1	54.9	Passed
4	94.8	4.7	53.0	Passed

Formation of lead chloride proceeds steadily with time up to the transition point, and all the sulphur is released in the elementary form, except, of course, about 8.0% that we had also seen earlier to be wasted or lost as sulphur dioxide. Beyond the transition point sulphur is rather quickly converted into its chlorides. Thus, by the direct reaction only about 70% of the original sulphur present in the sulphide is available as elementary sulphur, the reaction proceeding up to about 80%. Effect of use of incorporates was thus looked into with a view to further improving the yield.

Effect of different incorporates.—Effect of different incorporates was studied at 500°. The first one to be studied was carbon. The relevant results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Chlorination of PbS in presence of carbon.

PbS taken = 10 g. Ultra carbon taken = 1 g. *Temp. = 500°

Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Duration of expt.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. S found.	Transition point.
1 hr.	25.8%	73.6%	15.0%	Not reached
1 hr. 30 min.	42.0	57.3	32.8	Do
2	59.7	39.6	50.6	Do
2 40	79.7	19.8	70.6	Just reached
3	88.6	10.9	60.0	Passed at 2hr. 37min.
4	96.8	2.7	59.2	Passed at 2hr. 40 min.

In presence of carbon, the reaction proceeded smoothly at 500°. The product was powdery and not a hard and fused mass. No detailed study of the progress of chlorination of PbS alone at 500° was undertaken in view of the fact that even in three hours the progress of reaction was very small. A comparison of the results in Tables II and III would show that from the consideration of yield of elementary sulphur, use of carbon was no improvement over the chlorination of PbS alone at 400°.

Effect of silica.—Effect of silica was more or less the same as that with carbon. Results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
Chlorination of PbS in presence of silica.
PbS taken = 10 g. Silica (pptd.) taken = 2 g. Temp. = 500°.
Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Duration of expt.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. S found.	Nature of product.
1hr. 30 min.	46.2%	53.0%	37.0%	} Dry powdered mass, not fused. Transition point. passed at 2 hr. 10 min.
3	78.0	21.3	—	
3hr. 12 min.	83.8	18.8	71.0	
4	96.1	3.3	50.5	

With silica, the progress of chlorination (formation of PbCl₂) is slower but the transition point also comes later. The yield of elementary sulphur up to the transition point is nearly the same as in the presence of carbon. In these cases also, the product was a powdery mass, and not fused.

Effect of sodium chloride incorporate.—Chlorination in presence of sodium chloride proceeded most satisfactorily and therefore considerable number of experiments were carried out under these conditions. Results are shown in Table V.

TABLE V
Chlorination of PbS in presence of NaCl.
PbS taken = 10 g. NaCl taken = 2 g. Temp = 500°.
Rate of flow of Cl₂ = 6.35 c.c./min.

Duration of expt.	Progress of reaction.	Unchanged sulphide.	Elem. S formed.	Transition pt.
1 hr.	39.7%	60.0%	31.5%	Not reached
1hr. 30 min.	59.3	40.0	50.2	Not reached
2	77.6	22.0	68.6	Not reached
2 15 min.	83.3	16.3	74.0	Not reached
2 45 min.	88.0	11.0	79.6	Just reached
3	91.3	8.3	70.2	Passed at 2hr. 46 m.
4	97.3	2.3	60.0	Passed at 2hr. 45 m.
3 (a)	4.0	95.3	...	...
2hr. 40 min. (b)	80.4	19.0	70.5	Just reached

(a) Only mixture of PbS and NaCl heated, no chlorination.

(b) Reaction carried out at 400°.

It will be seen that the transition point is reached by about the same time as in presence of carbon ; but the total conversion of sulphide into lead chloride (88.0%) and the yield of elementary sulphur (79.6%) are both relatively high. From the results it appears that the conversion of lead sulphide into lead chloride is initially very high in presence of sodium chloride. In fact, a small amount of sulphur was found to collect in the cooler parts of the exit side of the reaction tube even before the starting of the chlorination. But the results of the blank experiments in Table V show that even in three hours, less than 5% of the lead sulphide is converted into the corresponding chloride, with NaCl alone. This points, however, that NaCl has some indirect accelerating (catalytic) effect on the chlorination.

Although the progress of reaction is rapid up to the transition point, it quickly slows down beyond this stage. This is reflected also in the rapidity with which sulphur is chlorinated (and thus decreasing the yield of sulphur). The product was somewhat fused mass. The fusion was due to the formation of a eutectic (m.p. nearly 400°) between sodium chloride and lead chloride. The eutectic requires only 27 molar percent of NaCl. And thus, the charge (10 g. PbS and 2 g. NaCl) contained sufficient excess of sodium chloride to decrease the fusibility, i.e. increase the fusion or melting point, of the product. An experiment was also done at a lower temperature (400°) so that the fusion effects might be further minimised. But, there the kinetic effects cause the transition point to reach at an earlier stage. On the whole, best results in the chlorination of lead sulphide was obtained in presence of sodium chloride. Under the most suitable conditions, nearly 80.0% of elementary sulphur can be obtained in the pure form in this way, while the chlorination proceeds to about 88%.

R E F E R E N C E S

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